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Knowledge of Media Tools and Marketing Efficiency among Groundnut Farmers in Ardo-Kola Local Government, Taraba State, Nigeria
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Abstract

The study analysed use of media tools for improved marketing activities among groundnut farmers in Ardo-kola local Government Area, Taraba State, Nigeria. A multi-stage sampling procedure was used to select 60 respondents. Data were analysed using percentages. The result revealed that 100% of the groundnut farmers had knowledge of each of the following: newspaper adverts, banners, television adverts, radio adverts, words-of- mouth, signboards and billboard as tools for marketing their produce. Also, words-of-mouth ($\bar{x} = 4.19$), facebook ($\bar{x} = 3.80$) and Trade fairs ($\bar{x}=3.74$) are the major media marketing tools use. the benefit of using media marketing include access to unlimited geographical location (88%), less expensive nature of media marketing (85%), and its accessibility (75%).The major constraints to the use of media marketing include unstable power supply (92%), high cost of devices used for media marketing (70%) and network failure (63%). The effective utilization of various media marketing tools is hindered by challenges such as unstable power supply and high device costs. Stakeholders in the agricultural sector, particularly the groundnut farmers should prioritize the establishment of reliable and affordable power supply solutions. This could include partnerships with government initiatives aimed at increasing access to stable electricity, thereby enabling them to effectively utilize media marketing tools without disruptions.

Keywords: Media marketing tools, knowledge of media tools, improved marketing activities.

Introduction

Groundnut (*Arachis hypogea L.*) is an important cash crop which provides source of livelihood to smallholder farmers. It is usually grown as a smallholder crop in the semi-arid tropics under rain fed conditions. The crop is important in many countries, especially in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), where it is a good source of protein (25%-34%), cooking oil (48%-50%) and vitamins (Jaji et al., 2023). The haulms are a good source of feed for livestock, especially during the dry season when fresh green grasses are not available, this serves as an additional source of income for farmers in the dry season when the haulms are in high demand. However, groundnut generates low economic benefits to small and medium scale farmers due to numerous marketing problems. Some of the marketing problems include lack of adequate or faulty marketing systems and strategies, instability in groundnut

production and price (Ahmed et al., 2021). Furthermore, Dauna et al. (2025) identified poor market outlet, and exploitative nature of middlemen who seem to be more actively involved in marketing and sales of the produce. In addition, Ajegen et al. (2022) opined poor market information system as another marketing problem. Also, poor roads, underutilization of research findings by farmers, lack of required modern marketing skills and lack of wider awareness about media marketing tools constitute marketing problems (Abubakar, 2024).

Media marketing tools are product development, promotional strategies and action that a company or farmer can use to develop and promote its produce, products or services. They are also channels, applications, networks, innovations, and platforms developed for marketing produce (Konoplyannikova et al., 2024). According to Ningsih (2024), examples of agricultural media marketing tools are market research surveys, television commercials, print advertisements, word-of-mouth (WOM), radio jingles, news releases, promotional items, road shows, agricultural exhibitions, customer loyalty programme, news media, pop-up adverts, search engine optimisation, mobile marketing and all digital media applications.

The advent of media marketing tools (MMTs) has revolutionized the way people advertise and market their produce worldwide. In a growing number of developed and developing countries, MMTs are being used to drive, increase, and market groundnut produce effectively, often with positive dramatic results (Ohara et al., 2024). Media marketing tools are useful in this highly dynamic, competitive, fast-paced, high technological advanced and global marketplace generation. Part of the goals of agricultural media marketing tools for agricultural produce is to showcase products and services that customers/potential customers will buy through different platforms, help farmers in increasing produce/farm exposure, broaden customer reach, analyse customer needs, satisfy them and reap benefits (Alzubi, 2023). According to Olajide and Opeyemi (2024), the use of media marketing tools helps in processing marketing information related to agricultural product and promotion. Despite the potential of various media tools to enhance marketing, promote products, and improve market access, many farmers lack the knowledge or resources to effectively harness these tools (Afolayan et al., 2024). This result in limited market visibility reduced sales opportunities, and inadequate awareness of best agricultural practices, ultimately affecting their income and sustainability. Base on this gap the study assessed the use of media tools for improved marketing activities among groundnut farmers in Ardo-kola local government area, Taraba State. The answered the following research questions; What are the respondents' knowledge on the use of media tools in groundnut marketing? What are the benefits achieved by the farmers in using media tools for marketing their groundnut? And what are the constraints to the use of media toolsfor improved marketing activities among groundnut farmers?

Methodology

The study was conducted in Ardo-kola Local Government Area of Taraba State. It is located between latitudes 8°35'N to 9°08'N and longitudes 10°52'E to 11°35'E east of the Greenwich meridian. The area has a total land size of about 2,262km². with an estimated population of about 86,921 and the present projected population of 2024 is 117,166 (Taraba State Government Diary 2025).

The population of this study comprised of the entire groundnut farmers in Ardo-kola Local Government Area.

Multi-stage sampling procedure was adopted to select respondents. The first stage involved a purposive selection of five wards out of ten wards of Ardo-kola Local Government area where groundnut is predominately produce. Stage two, two villages were selected from each selected wards using simple random sampling. Snow ball sampling technique was used to select 60 respondents for the study

. The Primary data were obtained through the use of structured interview schedule. Data were analysed using percentages.

Measurement Variable

The list of marketing tools was provided to groundnut farmers, and they were asked to identify which tools they are knowledgeable about and the type of marketing tools they used for their groundnut marketing. The use of marketing tools were measured using four point liker type scale of never = 1, rarely =2, sometime =3, often =4, very often =5. where respondents rank each marketing tools from 1 to 5 based on their level of agreement.

The list of perceived benefits and constraints of using media marketing tools was provided to groundnut farmers to assess their perceptions of the advantages and limitations associated with media marketing tools

Results and Discussion

Groundnut Farmers' Knowledge of the Use of Media Tools for Improved Marketing

The result in Table 1 revealed that 100% of the groundnut farmers had knowledge of each of the following: newspaper adverts, banners, television adverts, radio adverts, words-of-mouth signboards and billboard as tools for marketing their groundnut. Groundnut farmers' awareness of newspapers may indicate a broad recognition of print media as a marketing channel, potentially stemming from the widespread availability of newspapers within their community or prior exposure to marketing initiatives. While familiarity with newspaper advertisements could influence farmers' willingness or capacity to utilize print media for marketing purposes, it is important to note that awareness alone does not necessarily translate into active usage. Additionally, all surveyed farmers identified banners as an effective marketing tool. The widespread use and accessibility of banners suggest a familiarity with visual, on-site advertising methods that can facilitate local sales and attract immediate attention from passersby. Moreover, all farmers acknowledged the significance of personal communication and reputation management in marketing strategies. The reliance on personal networks and trust underscores the importance of social and community-based marketing approaches within rural contexts. These findings highlight the role of both print and visual advertising, as well as interpersonal relationships, in shaping marketing practices among groundnut farmers. Also 90% of the groundnut farmers had knowledge of the use of posters and flyers. The unanimous recognition of these media tools suggests that farmers are likely to utilize these tools to enhance their marketing efforts, potentially leading to increased sales and market competitiveness also this high level of awareness may also indicate an opportunity for educational

initiatives to explore and enhance existing knowledge, focusing on integrating digital marketing strategies alongside traditional methods. This corroborates the findings of Adedokun et al. (2020) that most cassava farmers in Oyo State were aware of MMTs based on their availability. Also, in the study of Kwaghtser (2024) on knowledge and use of social media platforms for marketing among farmers in Semi-urban Areas in Benue State revealed that many farmers in semi-urban areas in Benue State were aware of social media platforms and have attempted to use one social media platform or the other.

Table 1: Groundnut farmers’ knowledge of the use of media tools for improved marketing

*Media marketing tools	Percentage (N= 60)
Newspaper (Advertisement)	100
Banners	100
Television (Advertisement)	100
Radio (Advertisement)	100
Words-of-Mouth	100
Signboards	100
Billboard (non-electronic)	100
Posters	90
Flyers	90
Facebook	72
Stickers	70
Trade fairs	65
Road shows	55
Business cards	40
Cinema	32
Promotional gift items	30
WhatsApp	27
SMS	18
Instagram	13
Billboards (electronic)	8
Twitter	7
E-mail	7

Source: Field survey, 2024 * Multiple choices

Media Marketing Tools used by Groundnut Farmers

Result in table 2 shows that Words-of-mouth ($\bar{x} = 4.19$) is the most utilized and influential marketing tool among groundnut farmers. The high mean indicates that farmers rely heavily on personal recommendations and peer communications to

market their groundnuts. Its relatively high standard deviation suggests variability in usage, possibly reflecting differences in social networks or trust levels within communities. This method is cost-effective and trusted, often leading to organic dissemination of information. This study is in agreement with the study of Ismail et al. (2024) that words of mouth dimensions significantly influence the delivery of words of mouth messages, which in turn has a significant influence on market participation among smallholder farmers. Also, the result shows that facebook ($\bar{X} = 3.80$) holds significant relevance as a digital marketing platform. Farmers likely use it to reach broader audiences, share product information, or connect with buyers. The high standard deviation indicates varying levels of adoption, perhaps influenced by access to smartphones, internet connectivity, or digital literacy. Afolayan et al. (2024) Consider that Facebook offers tangible benefits by enhancing the promotion of new sales opportunities, leading to increased revenue through acquiring new customers, expanding into new markets, and leveraging existing customer relationships. Furthermore, the result shows that Trade fairs ($\bar{X} = 3.74$) serve as critical platforms for direct interaction with buyers, suppliers, and industry stakeholders. The substantial mean score suggests regular participation or at least recognition of their importance. Variability may be due to farmers' availability, resources to attend, or awareness of such events.

Table 2: Media Marketing Tools used by groundnut farmers

Media marketing tools	Mean	Std. Deviation
Words-of-Mouth	4.19	1.23236
Facebook	3.80	1.55314
Trade fairs	3.74	1.44763
Radio (Advertisement)	3.69	1.54800
Newspaper (Advertisement)	3.69	1.56022
Signboards	3.56	1.58799
Billboard (non-electronic)	3.24	1.66108
Posters	3.19	1.62352
Television (Advertisement)	3.18	1.66058
Banners	1.94	1.51147

Source: Field survey, 2024

Benefits Achieved by Groundnut Farmers in Using Media Tools for Marketing

The findings in Table 3 reveal that access to unlimited geographical reach, reported by 88% of groundnut farmers, constitutes one of the primary advantages of utilizing media tools for marketing. This suggests that most respondents recognize the significant benefit of being able to connect with customers across any location. Digital platforms effectively eliminate geographical barriers, enabling farmers to extend their market reach beyond local confines and access national or international

audiences. Such expansive accessibility can enhance brand visibility and create additional sales opportunities. These results corroborate the study conducted by Nwoye et al. (2022), which identified easy access to an unlimited geographical scope as a key perceived benefit of digital marketing.

Furthermore, the study indicates that 85% of respondents value the affordability of digital marketing tools. This underscores the importance of cost-effectiveness, as digital marketing typically demands lower financial investment compared to traditional advertising channels such as television or print media. The reduced costs allow groundnut farmers and small enterprises to compete more effectively and allocate resources to other critical operational areas.

In addition, 75% of respondents highlighted the accessibility of media tools as a significant benefit. Accessibility pertains to the ease with which both businesses and consumers can engage with online platforms. User-friendly interfaces and a strong online presence facilitate easier product discovery, browsing, and purchasing, thereby enhancing customer experience and satisfaction. These findings align with those of Nwoye et al. (2022), who noted that digital marketing’s perceived benefits include lower costs, convenient store hours, and an expanded customer base, ultimately leading to increased sales and profits

Table 3: Benefits achieved by groundnut farmers in using media tools for marketing

*Benefits of media marketing tools	Percentage (N= 60)
Access to unlimited geographical location	88
Less expensive	85
Accessibility	75
Convenient store hours	65
Access to information	57
Increased customer base	57
Increased sales	57
Increase in profit	50
Satisfaction	45
Provision for customized products	42

Source: Field survey, 2024 * Multiple choices

Constraints to the Use of Media Tools for Improved Marketing Activities among Groundnut Farmers

The findings presented in Table 4 indicate that unstable power supply is the predominant constraint affecting the use of media tools for improved marketing activities among groundnut farmers, with 92% of respondents citing this issue. This suggests that a significant majority of farmers face challenges related to inconsistent electricity availability, which hampers their ability to effectively utilize electronic media devices such as smartphones, computers, and other digital tools essential for

modern marketing efforts. The lack of reliable power disrupts access to online platforms, communication channels, and the operation of electronic devices, thereby limiting farmers' engagement with digital marketing strategies.

Additionally, the high cost of devices necessary for media-based marketing is identified as a major barrier, with 70% of farmers reporting expenses related to acquiring smartphones, tablets, or computers as a significant obstacle. This financial constraint restricts farmers' capacity to participate fully in digital marketing activities, which are increasingly important for expanding market reach, negotiating better prices, and establishing reliable networks. Furthermore, network failure was also reported as a major constraint, affecting 63% of farmers, and further impeding the effective use of media tools for marketing.

The results align with previous studies, notably those by Adedokun et al. (2020), which highlighted that high device costs and lack of technical know-how hinder farmers' use of media marketing tools (MMTs). Similarly, Adedokun et al. (2021) found that insufficient knowledge of MMTs also significantly affects their adoption among farmers, emphasizing the importance of capacity building and infrastructural development to support digital marketing initiatives in rural agricultural communities.

Table 4: Constraints to the use of media tools for improved marketing activities among groundnut farmers

*Constraints	Percentage (N=60)
Unstable power supply	92
High cost of the devices for accessing MMTs	70
Network failure	63
Lack of technical know how	60
High cost of operating MMTs	57
Inadequate market information	48
Hazard through radioactive emission of the devices	37
Cost of batteries	28
Irrelevant content	22
Wrong time of the programme	15

Source: Field survey, 2024 * Multiple choices

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings of this research, conclusion can be drawn that groundnut farmers had knowledge of each of the following: newspaper adverts, banners, television adverts, radio adverts, words-of mouth signboards and billboard, as tools for marketing their produce. Also, the benefits of using media marketing include access to unlimited geographical location, less expensive nature of media tools, its accessibility, convenient store hours, easy access to information, increased

customer base, increased sales, and increase in profit. The major constraint to the use of media tools include unstable power supply, high cost of devices for accessing media marketing tools, and network failure as constraints associated with the use of media tools. Stakeholders in the agricultural sector, particularly the groundnut farmers, should prioritize the establishment of reliable and affordable power supply solutions. This could include partnerships with renewable energy providers or government initiatives aimed at increasing access to stable electricity, thereby enabling them to effectively utilize media marketing tools without disruptions. There is need for all concerned stakeholders (government, non-governmental organisations, ministries of agriculture, agricultural development agencies and media houses) to subsidize the cost of media devices and data. This will motivate farmers to frequently use the media tools for their groundnut marketing.

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